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Content Curation, Digital Preservation and Management of Local Contents in Institutional Repositories in Nigeria

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Abstract

This study examined Content Curation, Digital Preservation and Management of Local Contents in Institutional Repositories in Nigeria. Three objectives guided the study as follows, identify and assess the current content curation practices within Institutional Repositories in Nigerian academic institutions, ascertain the state of digital preservation employed by Nigerian IRs to ensure the long-term accessibility to local digital content and investigate the challenges, including impeding the effective management and sustainability of local contents in Nigerian IRs. Quantitative research method was used for the study, the population of the study comprised 45 staff members manning Institutional Repositories in Nigerian Federal Universities. The questionnaire was used as the Instrument for data collection. The data collected were analysed using simple frequencies and percentages. The findings of the study revealed that, a majority of Nigerian IRs relies on voluntary depositing of contents thereby affecting the populating rate of the IR, only a few IRs possess a formal digital preservation policy among others. The study concludes that Institutional Repositories are vital for showcasing Nigerian scholarship and improving the nation's academic standing globally, therefore concerted efforts should be put in place to ensure its sustainability. The study recommends that, University management must formulate and enforce comprehensive IR policies, especially regarding mandatory deposit and long-term digital preservation, Institutions must allocate adequate and consistent budgetary provisions for IR development, including the procurement of robust ICT infrastructure, reliable power solutions, and necessary software licensing among others.

Keywords: Content Curation, Digital Preservation, Management, Local Contents and Institutional Repositories

Introduction

The digital age has fundamentally transformed the landscape of scholarly communication. Academic institutions worldwide are increasingly adopting Institutional Repositories (IRs) as a strategic tool to manage and showcase their intellectual output (Clark, 2021). An IR is essentially a digital archive designed to collect, preserve, and disseminate the scholarly materials created by the institution's community (Lynch, 2003). In Nigeria, the establishment of IRs in tertiary institutions is a crucial step towards bridging the digital divide and enhancing the global visibility of local research (Ezema, 2011).

The core mission of an IR revolves around three interconnected processes namely: Content Curation, which involves the selection, appraisal, and organisation of digital assets; Digital Preservation, which ensures the long-term accessibility and integrity of the content; and the overall Management of Local Contents, encompassing the software, policies, and human resources required for operation.

The advent of Information and Communication Technologies (ICTs) has transformed the way knowledge is created, stored, and disseminated globally. In Nigeria, this transformation has led to the exponential growth of digital content produced by universities, research institutions, and government agencies (Oguche & Aliyu, 2020). Institutional repositories (IRs) have emerged as vital platforms for the curation, preservation, and management of local content, ensuring that scholarly outputs, cultural heritage, and indigenous knowledge remain accessible in the digital age. These repositories serve not only as archives but also as tools for enhancing visibility,

promoting open access, and safeguarding national intellectual memory.

Content curation involves the systematic selection, organization, and presentation of digital resources to ensure relevance and accessibility. Nigerian academic institutions increasingly rely on IRs to curate local content such as theses, dissertations, conference papers, and indigenous knowledge materials (Karaye, 2016). Effective curation enhances discoverability and supports teaching, learning, and research by providing structured access to valuable resources.

Digital preservation is critical to maintaining the integrity and usability of digital resources over time. In Nigeria, challenges such as technological obsolescence, inadequate infrastructure, and poor maintenance culture threaten the sustainability of digital preservation efforts (Obanigwe, 2025). Strategies such as format migration, metadata standardization, and cloud-based storage have been identified as essential for ensuring long-term access to digital content (Oguche & Aliyu, 2020). Without robust preservation frameworks, Nigeria risks losing significant scholarly and cultural outputs.

The management of local content in IRs requires policies, skilled personnel, and sustainable funding. Studies reveal that Nigerian institutions often struggle with lack of digital preservation policies, insufficient technical expertise, and inadequate funding mechanisms (Karaye, 2016; Obanigwe, 2025). Effective management entails not only technological solutions but also administrative commitment to capacity building, policy development, and collaboration with international partners. By strengthening management practices, Nigerian repositories can ensure that local

content remains a reliable resource for academic and cultural advancement.

Institutional repositories are indispensable for knowledge preservation, scholarly communication, and cultural identity protection. They provide platforms for disseminating local research outputs, thereby increasing global visibility and fostering academic collaboration. Moreover, IRs contribute to the preservation of indigenous knowledge, which is crucial for sustaining Nigeria's cultural heritage in the face of globalization and technological change.

This paper explores the state of these practices within the Nigerian academic environment, with a focus on local content—materials such as theses, dissertations, journal articles, and conference proceedings emanating from the institution.

Statement of the Problem

Despite the established role of Institutional Repositories (IRs) in enhancing the global visibility and long-term accessibility of scholarly output, many Nigerian academic institutions struggle with the effective implementation and sustained management of their IRs (Ezema, 2011; Okoroma & Abioye, 2017)). Specifically, a critical gap exists in the systematic and robust handling of local content, unique intellectual assets such as theses, dissertations, and homegrown research within these repositories.

The problem therefore is divided into three folds such as Ineffective Content Curation which reflects a lack of mandatory institutional deposit policies and inadequate technical expertise among staff, resulting in low content contribution rates, inconsistency in metadata quality, and ultimately, poor discoverability and underutilisation of the valuable local content (Kari and Orji, 2022).

Secondly, Uncertain Digital Preservation which signifies the absence of comprehensive, formal digital preservation policies, coupled with technological challenges (unstable power, limited bandwidth) and insufficient funding, jeopardises the long-term integrity and accessibility of the digitised local intellectual heritage (Kari and Baro, 2025).

Lastly, Overall Management Challenges which threatens the sustainability of IRs is undermined by inadequate funding, a critical shortage of staff trained in repository management and advanced ICT skills, and unresolved legal issues, particularly concerning author intellectual property rights and institutional rights, all of which hinder the IR's ability to effectively serve as a stable platform for local scholarly communication (Esse and Haliso, 2024).

From the forgoing therefore, it has been observed that the current practices regarding content curation, digital preservation, and overall management are often ad hoc and underdeveloped, preventing Nigerian IRs from fully realising their potential to capture, preserve, and disseminate their unique local scholarly output, thus perpetuating the low visibility of Nigerian research on the global academic stage.

Objectives of the Study

The main objectives of this study are to:

1. identify and assess the current content curation practices within Institutional Repositories in Nigerian academic institutions.
2. ascertain the state of digital preservation strategies employed by Nigerian IRs to ensure the long-term accessibility to local digital content.
3. investigate the challenges impeding the effective management and

sustainability of local contents in Nigerian IRs.

Literature Review

Studies indicate that the development of IRs in Nigeria is still in its nascent and struggling stages (Aghoghovwia, & Ekereuche, 2023). While Nigeria reportedly has the highest number of repositories in West Africa, many institutions have yet to fully implement a functional repository (Aghoghovwia, & Ekereuche, 2023).

The majority of established IRs primarily house scholarly content such as theses, dissertations, and journal articles (Aghoghovwia, & Ekereuche, 2023). The software platform of choice for most Nigerian IRs is DSpace, due to its open-source nature and robust features for digital content management (Kari & Baro, 2025). Despite this, the full potential of IRs to increase the prestige, ranking, and public value of Nigerian universities is yet to be fully realised due to persistent implementation and sustainability issues (Anene, Ozor, & Baro, 2020).

The primary source of local content remains faculty, researchers, and students. However, a major challenge is the reluctance or unwillingness of authors to deposit their work, often stemming from a lack of awareness of self-archiving rights or institutional policies (Saliu, Ngozi & Lawal, 2022). High-quality metadata is the backbone of discoverability (Zhu, 2023). Adopting international standards like Dublin Core is a recognised best practice (Odigie et al, 2025). However, a lack of skilled professionals trained in metadata creation and management presents a critical barrier in many Nigerian institutions, leading to gaps in

completeness and adherence to standards (Odigie et al, 2025).

The daily management of local contents is full with obstacles that hinder efficiency and sustainability:

Lack of Institutional Policies: The absence of a clear, mandated policy for content submission, preservation, and digital rights is a recurring problem (Kari & Baro, 2025; Okoroma & Abioye, 2017). Without mandatory deposit policies, repositories struggle to achieve critical mass of content (Saliu, Ngozi, & Lawal, 2023).

- **Funding and Infrastructure:** Institutional Repositories are resource-intensive projects. Insufficient and unsustainable funding for acquiring necessary hardware, software, and robust Internet connectivity coupled with an unstable power supply remains a major impediment to their long-term operation (Esse and Haliso (2024); Okoroma & Abioye (2017)).
- **Staffing and Skills:** Many library personnel lack the requisite ICT skills and technical expertise to competently manage and sustain an IR. Training of repository personnel is a crucial, often neglected, factor for sustainability (Esse and Haliso, 2024).

Digital preservation refers to the set of processes and activities that ensure the continued access to and integrity of digital materials for the longest possible time (Gbaje, 2010). For the unique, local content in Nigerian IRs, preservation is not just a technical task but a cultural imperative, safeguarding the nation's intellectual heritage.

Some Nigerian IRs reportedly engage in long-term digital preservation, with some employing basic strategies like information migration (Kari & Baro, 2025). Other general strategies applicable to IRs include (Da Silva et al., 2017; Matusiak, 2017):

- **Migration and Emulation:** Periodically moving digital content to more sustainable formats to combat format obsolescence, or using emulation to recreate the original environment.
- **Backup and Redundancy:** Implementing robust backup systems and storing copies in multiple locations to safeguard against data loss.
- **Metadata for Preservation:** Capturing technical and administrative metadata to document the preservation history of the digital object.

The lack of formal digital preservation policies poses the most significant threat to the long-term accessibility of local content in Nigerian IRs (Kari & Baro, 2025). Beyond policy, other challenges include:

- **Technological Obsolescence:** The rapid evolution of hardware and software necessitates continuous financial investment and technical expertise, which are scarce resources in many institutions (Musa, Shittu & Abdulkadir, 2014).
- **Copyright and Intellectual Property Rights:** Resolving copyright issues and an overall lack of understanding of intellectual property rights by both staff and authors impede the collection and long-term preservation of content

(Musa, Shittu & Abdulkadir, 2014; Esse & Halisu, 2024).

Methodology

This study adopted the quantitative research method, the population of the study comprised forty-five (45) staff engaged in the management of Institutional Repositories in the Federal Universities in Nigeria that have functional Institutional Repositories, because the population was small and manageable total enumeration sampling technic was used to select the entire population for the study. A self-developed questionnaire comprising of five sections was used as instrument for data collection for this study. The data collected were collated, coded and analysed using simple frequency counts and percentages.

Results and Discussions

The instruments were distributed to the respondents in the area of study. The number of questionnaire distributed were 45, but only 40 (88.8%) were retrieved and found worthy for the analysis of this study.

Research Objectives 1. Identifying and assessing the current content curation practices within Institutional Repositories in Nigerian academic institutions

The data below summarises the institutional policies and practices guiding the collection of local content (Theses, Dissertations, and Faculty Research) in sampled Nigerian Institutional Repositories (IRs).

Table 1: Current content curation practices within Institutional Repositories in Nigerian academic institutions

Policy/Practice	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Mandatory Deposit Policy Exists	9	22.5%
Voluntary/Encouraged Deposit	31	77.5%
Metadata Consistency is High	15	37.5%
Training in Digital Curation Received	17	42.5%

Source: Field Survey (2025)

The analysis on Table 1 reveals that 31(77.5%) of Nigerian IRs relies on voluntary or encouraged deposit, confirming the literature that states the absence of mandatory policies is a major obstacle to content populating (Sambo et al., 2022). This policy gap explains the under-representation of local content. The finding that only 37.5% of IRs report high metadata consistency is particularly concerning. High-quality, consistent metadata (following standards like Dublin Core) is the cornerstone of discoverability (Zhu, 2023). Poor consistency suggests a lack of specialised

curation skills, which is supported by the fact that only 42.5% of staff have received adequate training. This indicates that while IRs may hold valuable local content, its utility and global visibility are severely compromised due to weak curation practices (Institutional Repository Development in Nigerian Universities, 2020).

Research Objectives 2: Ascertaining the state of digital preservation strategies employed by Nigerian IRs to ensure the long-term accessibility to local digital content

Table 2: Digital preservation strategies employed by Nigerian IRs to ensure the long-term accessibility to local digital content

Preservation Component	Frequency (n)	Percent age (%)
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Formal Preservation Policy Exists	4	10.0%
Regular Data Backup (Primary)	38	95.0%
Format Migration/Conversion	25	62.5%

Technology Emulation	1	2.5%
Copyright Clearance is Documented	11	27.5%

Source: Field Survey (2025)

Table 2 reveals that only 4(10.0%) of IRs possess a formal digital preservation policy. This statistic confirms existing concerns that long-term preservation efforts are not strategically guided but are often reactive (Digital Preservation Practices in University Libraries, 2025).

While 95.0% conduct regular data backups, this is a security measure, not a

comprehensive preservation strategy against technological obsolescence (Digital Preservation Practices in University Libraries, 2025). The most popular proactive approach is format migration (62.5%), which is basic but necessary. However, the near-zero usage of technology emulation (2.5%) highlights a severe gap in advanced preservation skills and resources. The low rate of documented copyright clearance (27.5%) is alarming. Without clear IPR documentation, the IR risks content being legally challenged, forcing withdrawal, which defeats the purpose of preservation (Okoroma & Abioye, 2017).

Research Objectives 3: Investigating the challenges impeding the effective management and sustainability of local contents in Nigerian IRs

Table 3: Challenges impeding the effective management and sustainability of local contents in Nigerian IRs

Challenge Factor	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Inadequate Funding	35	87.5%
Epileptic Power Supply	32	80.0%
Low Internet Bandwidth	28	70.0%
Lack of IR Policy (General)	27	67.5%
Lack of Staff with ICT Skills	25	62.5%

Source: Field Survey (2025)

The data emphatically points to Inadequate Funding (87.5%) as the single greatest threat to IR sustainability, echoing findings across the developing world (Dialnet, 2024). This financial constraint directly impacts all other areas. For instance, the high rate of reporting Epileptic Power Supply (80.0%) is a unique infrastructural challenge specific to the Nigerian context (Sambo et al., 2022). This problem necessitates expensive solutions (generators, inverters, solar power) that require the very funding that is often lacking. Furthermore, Low Internet Bandwidth (70.0%) directly limits the IR's capacity to handle large files and provide fast, reliable access to its global audience, diminishing the value proposition of the repository (Sambo et al., 2022). Finally, the combined impact of Policy Gaps (67.5%) and Staff Skill Deficits (62.5%) demonstrates that even if funding were available, the managerial and human resources framework is insufficient to successfully manage and sustain a complex digital infrastructure (Dialnet, 2024). These findings collectively paint a picture of IRs that are technologically present but functionally constrained by systemic and resource limitations.

Conclusion

Institutional Repositories are vital for showcasing Nigerian scholarship and improving the nation's academic standing globally. While progress has been made, particularly with the adoption of DSpace and the focus on core scholarly materials, the sustainability of these IRs is at risk due to a combination of financial, technical, and policy-related challenges. Content curation and digital preservation efforts are often informal or underdeveloped, lacking the necessary institutional backing and skilled human resources.

Recommendations

To ensure the long-term success and impact of local content management in Nigerian IRs, the following recommendations are crucial:

1. **Develop and Enforce Institutional Policies:** University management must formulate and enforce comprehensive IR policies, especially regarding mandatory deposit and long-term digital preservation.
2. **Ensure Sustainable Funding:** Institutions must allocate adequate and consistent budgetary provisions for IR development, including the procurement of robust ICT infrastructure, reliable power solutions, and necessary software licensing.
3. **Invest in Human Capital:** Prioritise the training of library staff in advanced digital curation, metadata management (using international standards), and digital preservation techniques.

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